

Gardening Simulator Based on L-System Algorithm

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Abstract—gardening simulator offers a new way for people to experience the joy gardening in the virtual simulated world without the expensive resource, the gardening simulator also can be used in the recreational, education, and research. One method that can be used in a more realistic gardening simulator is using the procedural generation method, Lindermayer System or L-system is one such principle used in procedural generation method as mathematical formula that consists of an alphabet as a symbol that can be used to make strings and can be carried recursively to make larger strings. To implement the L-system into the gardening simulator, we need to understand how the gardening simulator works by learning the early development of gardening simulator, the implementation of algorithm in the gardening simulator, the latest technology of creating 3d plants, and the implementation of L-system to simulate realistic plants. The L-system is able to demonstrate the growth of stem and root in the plant by iterating the algorithm and also, we can limit how plant grow using several factors such as humidity and light source, by using the L-System we able to create a 3d plant simulator more easily because it can produce 3d plants from a set of strings while simultaneously simulating their growth.

Keywords— *L-System, Procedural Generation, Gardening Simulator, Simulator, Virtual Environment.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Gardening is a one of hobby that can be enjoyed by people of all ages [1], from the study gardening have positive effect on health and minds, including stress relief, physical exercise, and allow the individual to feel connected to the nature and learn the environment works [2]. In this Simulator we can use in smart agriculture that offers the efficiency of gardening by harnessing the power of technology like sensors and data management.

However, the resource to maintain the physical garden is quite expensive and time consuming, gardening simulator offers a way for people to experience the joy gardening in the virtual simulated world.

Gardening simulation technology is a developing sector that provides users with a virtual gardening

environment. Users may create and develop their own virtual garden in the simulation, delivering an engaging and immersive experience [3]. With technological improvements, virtual gardens have gotten more realistic, giving users with a convincing recreation of the gardening experience.

There are several uses for gardening simulation technologies, including recreational, education, and research without using real plant. People also can use gardening simulator for the people who have hobby taking care a plant without spending money. For educational purpose this simulation can be used to teach student and observing the growth of plant. Some simulation also can be used as recreational simulator with gamify to make simulation more interactive and immersive.

One method that can be used in a more realistic gardening simulator is to use the procedural generation method, this will create plants semi-automatically using human-generated rules and random input rather than manually creating hundred assets for plants [4], by using procedural generation we can more effectively create realistic and diverse plant in the simulator.

Lindermayer System or L-system is one such principle used in procedural generation. L-system were first introduced by biologist Aristid Lindermayer in 1968 [5] as mathematical formula that consists of an alphabet as a symbol that can be used to make strings and can be carried recursively to make larger strings. The history of L-System is based on Chomsky Grammar in 1957, while they both using some formula with production rule to generate strings, Chomsky grammar apply that production rule sequentially where L-system apply them in parallel by replacing all letter in a given word simultaneously which make L-system more popular.[6]

This paper explores how gardening simulators work and how L-systems can be used in gardening simulators to create realistic plant growth patterns. We introduce the basic concepts of L-systems, including production rules, variables, and constants. We then describe how L-systems can be used to model plant growth,

including the formation of branches, leaves and stems, and the development of flowers and fruit, to demonstrate the effectiveness of L-System in.

This paper also discussing how L-systems can be combined with other technique such as physical simulation and can be implemented in the gardening simulator using Unity with 3D models and texture mapping, by using the L-System we able create a 3d plant simulator more easily because it can produce 3d plants from a set of strings while simultaneously simulating their growth

II. RELATED WORKS

To implement the L-system into the gardening simulator, we need to understand how the gardening simulator works by learning the concept of L-System in early era, implementation of algorithm in the gardening simulator, the latest technology of creating 3d plants to compare alternative method of creating 3d plants, the implementation of L-system to simulate realistic plants.

A. Concept of L-System

Initially the L-system was a parallel rewriting system and a type of formal grammar introduced and developed in 1968 by Aristid Lindenmayer, a Hungarian theoretical biologist and botanist at the University of Utrecht [7]. Aristid Lindenmayer formulated the use of strings repeatedly to create geometric shapes, an easy example is in the figure below:

Iteration	Result
0	A
1	AB
2	ABA
3	ABAAB
4	ABAABABA
5	ABAABABAABAAB

Fig 1. Example of L-System

In figure 1. We can see that there are two variables, A and B, the 0th iteration is also called an axiom, in fig 1. Using the rule of changing A to AB and B to A in each iteration. With the same method we can create a simple plant model with the model is depicted through a string, where the axiom symbolizes the model's starting condition. During each cycle, every character within the current string, which initially is the axiom, gets substituted with a string of characters determined by the corresponding reproduction guidelines. For instance, if the Axiom is 'F,' and the 'F-Reproduction' rule is applied, it transforms into 'FX,' and similarly for the 'X-Reproduction.' "F" means: Move forward by a constant length and draw a line; "f" means: Move forward by the same constant length and don't draw a line; "+" means: Turn right by a given angle, "-" means: Turn left by the same angle. The symbol "[" stores the current position and angle, whereas the symbol "]" restores the last position and angle, i.e., jumps back to the last "[" [8]. For example, we able to create simple branch in [8] with the rule:

$$'F' \rightarrow F[-F] + F, \text{ with angle} = 15 \text{ and iteration} = 2 \quad (1)$$

Fig 2. Example of L-System using [8]

B. Implementation of Algorithm into gardening simulators

One of most recent of gardening simulation using the mathematical equation algorithm is AlphaGardenSim from [3] they make a simulation of polyculture farming, with polyculture farming they can grow multiple different breeds of plant with automation. In their work they able to make a fast and first order simulation that use the plant growth models to simulate polyculture farming with automation system.

The method that used by AlphaGardenSim [3], use modeled garden as a discrete $M \times N$ grid Each point $p(x, y)$ in the garden contains up to one seed, and up to a fixed capacity of water. They define $D(k)$ as a set of k plant types available in the garden, as well as types soil and unknown. At each point $p(x, y)$ in the garden at time t , we define $d(x,y,t)$, a vector of length k representing the distribution of the plant (or soil) types that is visible overhead at point $p(x,y)$, the use a different local and global variable that using the time dependent state variables.

TABLE I. Local and Global State Variables in [3]

Local Variable			
$d(x,y,t)$	$h(x,y,t)$	$w(x,y,t)$	$s(x,y)$
Plant Type	Plant Health	Water Amount	Seed Location
Global Variable			
$p(k,t)$	$e(t)$	$v(t)$	$s(t)$
Plant Distribution	Total Canopy Coverage	Garden diversity	Garden Sustainability

Unlike the AlphaGardenSim, the AquaCrop [9] using monocultural farming with large scale operation using point-based models, which make the assumption that plants are grown homogeneously. Therefore, these models are not well-suited for a polyculture setting, where gardens are heterogeneous. Their work focused using the models that water will affect growth of plant, and reusing the climate to revolve water cycle.

From two paper [3][9], we can see the differences of algorithm that they use will affect the factor of plant growth, so before we work into the simulator, we need to limit the factor that affect plant growth, the more factor we need, the more realistic the simulator we can create, but adding the more factor will increase the load of computer, that's why we need to sorting the factor we need in this simulator.

C. How to create 3D plant technologies.

To make a plant simulator we need to be able to make 3D plant models, there are many ways to make 3D plant models, one of which is to create a single 3d asset and then animate it to simulate its growth, but this is very inefficient because it takes a long time to make. and lots of resources, paper [10] proposes the theory of using 3d scans to represent 3d models of real plants.

Fig 2. The result of 3d scanning of plants by paper [9]

The 3D point clouds of plant on paper [9] are one of method to replicate the plant into 3d world, by scanning the real plant. The proposed technique of paper [9] consists of three main steps: pre-processing, point matching, and refinement. In the pre-processing step, the 3D point clouds are first segmented to remove unwanted parts such as the ground or the pot. Then, the point clouds are normalized to a common reference frame to reduce the variability in their position and orientation.

In the point matching step, the normalized point clouds are matched using a non-rigid registration algorithm that can handle the deformations and non-linear transformations that occur during plant growth. The algorithm uses a feature-based approach that extracts key points from the point clouds and matches them based on their local geometry and descriptors. The algorithm also uses a hierarchical search strategy that progressively refines the matching based on the similarity of the local neighborhoods. In the refinement step, the matched point clouds are further refined to improve their alignment and accuracy. The refinement uses a deformation field that models the local deformations between the point clouds and applies it to the points in one cloud to align them with the other cloud. The deformation field is computed using a Gaussian process regression that can model the non-linear and non-stationary nature of the deformations.

The advantage of using this method is that it can produce 3D plants whose shape is exactly the same as the original plant, but this method requires quite a long time to make the 3D model because the 3D model follows the original growth time of the plant.

D. Implementation L – System to simulate plant growth.

Instead scanning each plant using 3d scanner like in the paper [10], we can work more efficient by using mathematical formula to simulate the plant growth, paper [11] proposed intelligent approach how to model realistic tree models using semi-automatic generated L-systems by modify the L-system to create 3D tree instead 2D tree, the approach is different from traditional methods that require manual modeling and can be time-consuming and labor-intensive. The proposed method uses a combination of

genetic algorithms and L-systems to generate tree models that are both realistic and efficient. The paper [11] discusses the details of the proposed method, including its input requirements, output variables, and limitations. It also provides examples of tree models generated using the proposed method and compares them with real-life trees to demonstrate their realism.

Their L system work by paper [11] interpreted set of rules by using the alphabet, each alphabet will be recurse to create the branch from initial axiom, the command that used in paper [11] is:

TABLE II. the command of rule that used in [10]

Command	Action
F(d)	Move forward a step of length d
f(d)	Forward a step of d, without drawing the line
+(δ)	Turn left by angle δ around the Y axis.
-(δ)	Turn right by angle δ around the Y axis.
&(δ)	Pitch down by angle δ around the X axis.
^(δ)	Pitch up by angle δ around the X axis
\(δ)	Roll left by angle δ around the Z axis.
/(δ)	Roll right by angle δ around the Z axis.
[Push the current state of the turtle to stack.
]	Pop the current state of the turtle from stack.
@S(id)	Drawing the surface with the specified id.

The command then can be used to create the formula of creating Tree. For example, of creating tree X:

$$'X' \rightarrow F(30)[/(+30)X][-(30)X]\backslash X[+(30)F(30)]X[-(30)F]\backslash X \quad (1)$$

from this formula, the value of x will be recursive, the more recursion is done, the more branches of the tree X will be, can be seen in figure 4:

Fig 4. The result of paper [11] L-System

III. METHOD

Our approach can be seen as how L-system can be modified to simulate the plant growth and then animate it, for this, we need to modify the L system from paper [11] to create another part of tree like the root, the flower, and the fruit, and adding the condition factor of plant growth.

First instead using the length and angle in the command like in the paper [11], we can simplify the command, by initialize the desired length and angle first.

TABLE III. the Command of rule that we use in our research

Command	Action
F	Draw branch in the tree structure, using 2d line in unity,
L	Draw the leaf spawn in the initial axiom by using leaf prefab (unity billboard image)
M	Draw the fruit spawn point in the initial axiom by using melon fruit prefab (3d object)
R	Draw the Root (similar way to create branch but upside down)
+	Rotate the transformation in the clockwise direction
-	Rotate the transformation in the counter clockwise direction
*	Rotates the transform by 120 degrees in the clockwise direction around its y-axis to create 3d Tree. The rotation angle is calculated in the same way as in cases '+' and '-'.
/	Rotates the transform by 120 degrees in the counter clockwise direction around its y-axis to create 3d Tree. The rotation angle is calculated in the same way as in cases '+' and '-'.
[pushes a new Transform Info object onto the transform Stack
]	pops the last Transform Info object from the transform Stack and sets the transform's position and rotation to the values stored in the object

From table 3 we able to replicate melon tree using the prototype asset by using this equation:

$$'X' \rightarrow "FL[/+X][M][-X] * X[+F]X[-F] * X" \quad (1)$$

$$'F' \rightarrow FFL \quad (2)$$

$$'M' \rightarrow "[+M]" \quad (3)$$

we use a different equation to simulate plant roots is because the roots and stems will have different behavior, the roots are not directly affected by light and the root didn't have leaf. The equation for the root system is:

$$'X' \rightarrow "R[/+X][-X] * X[+X]X[-X] * X" \quad (4)$$

$$'F' \rightarrow FF \quad (5)$$

The result of that equation with branch angle = 30, branch length = 6f, branch iteration = 3, root angle = 25, root length = 3f, and root iteration = 4 will produce tree in figure 2

Initialize Variables:

- lightning_distance (distance between the plant and the lightning)
- lightning_intensity (intensity of the lightning)
- iteration_speed (initial iteration speed)
- fog_emission (current fog speed)
- time_interval (time interval for updates)

Main Loop:

```
While the game is running:
- Get lightning_distance between the player and the lightning
- Get lightning_intensity from the lightning
- Get current fog_emission

- If lightning_distance is getting closer:
- Increase iteration_speed

- If lightning_intensity is increasing:
- Increase iteration_speed

- If fog is getting faster:
- Increase iteration_speed

- Perform iterations at the current iteration_speed

- Wait for time_interval before the next iteration
```


Fig 5. The tree from that equation

From table 3 we can see instead creating Fruit in The L system, we only creating the spawn point. This method is used because the in the L system that we use does not make a 3d mesh on the branches, instead using a 2d line that is locked always facing the camera to optimize performance so that the L-system can run many plants at once, by using this method we can use physical simulator in unity, like gravitation, wind current, and rigid body to create more realistic plant without sacrifice the perform.

And then we will animate growth of tree by using transform size in unity, by transforming the size from 0 to 1 to create grow effect. The transformation will be executed in each iteration. Then we add factors for the condition of the tree to grow, by limiting iterations by several factors:

TABLE IV. The Factor that affects the growth of the plant.

Factor	Action
sun direction	Change the angle of the L-system formula to towards the sun
Sun light	Change the plant angle based the intensity of the sun light
humidity	Change the plant size based the intensity of humidity
Time	Change the plant size by each time

To simulate the sun direction and sun light intensity we use unity engine lightning that able to simulate lighting physic based on the intensity of the light, then we use fog system in unity engine as source of humidity, we can control the intensity of fog emission rate over time to create more foggy (more humid condition), the light and fog will be controlling the iteration time for simulate the plant growth. Brief details of light and humidity can be seen in the pseudo code below:

IV. RESULT

The result of this research is to integrated L-system into gardening simulator with various plant behavior, the result is we able to grow simulator plants with L-system but the plant growth is controlled by sun light and humidity.

Fig 6. Plant Growth using Recursion of L-system with controlled behavior.

From the figure 3, we can see the tree that we create using L-system and combined with Factor that affect growth of the plant. The plants in only able to grow if there is enough sunlight and humidity.

Fig 7. Fruit Spawn Point (green ball) in the simulated tree

We are also able to integrate the fruit spawn point in the simulated tree, the spawn point will be a place for fruit to grow in the simulated plant in future projects. The green balls will be replaced by actual fruit that grow based on the various factor.

Fig 8. The Variance of tree with one L-System Formula.

We also implement tree variance in the L system so that we can create completely different plants using just one L system formula shown in figure 5, with this we can use one string to create several plants of the same type. each plant has a unique shape, in this case the L-System is very helpful in making 3d plants because it can shorten the time compared to making 3d plants manually

Fig 9. Final Result of Garden Simulator Using L-System

The final result of gardening simulator using L-System is we are able to recreate the plant in the hydroponic Dutch bucket in digital world, in this simulation we use lamp as source of the light and fog as the source of humidity.

V. CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, our gardening simulator using L-System algorithm is able to demonstrate the growth of plant with several factors such as humidity and sun light and time. We can control how plant grows by manipulating humidity level. In this simulator we can see the progress of plant growth both from the stems and roots.

While our study has provided valuable insights into the capabilities of our gardening simulator, there are still many avenues for future research. One potential limitation of our study is that we only examined the effects of two variables (lighting and humidity) on plant growth performance. Future studies could explore the effects of other variables, such as temperature, water availability, soil type and another variety

of plants on virtual plant growth and behavior. For future studies we want this simulator able to demonstrate plant growth with another organ, such as flower and fruit.

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